

HANGING ON FIRE! DEBATES ON WOMEN'S RESERVATION IN INDIAN POLITICS: A CINEMATIC CONTEMPLATION

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ABSTRACT

Gender discrimination is one of the essential causes to relegate the position of women in the political arena of India. It is a ground for denying rights and is not an argument posited in opposition to the notion of universal rights of women. In the political sphere, there is no equality for women either. Throughout India, except for voters, women's participation as contestants, elected representatives, members of the Government, and so on was negligible. Regional and sectional patterns in political participation manifest themselves with familiar correlations. The nature of problems is varied, such as lack of time due to domestic responsibilities, sociocultural norms limiting mobility, and patriarchal control discouraging women from coming into conflict with men. Patriarchy is indicated as ramparts between public and private for women. The inner-outer distinction specified that the world is external, the domain of material, and the home represents the inner spiritual self. The world is typically a treacherous terrain of pursuing material interests where practical consideration reigns supreme. It is also eventually the domain of the male. In 2015, the Report on the Status of Women in India perceived that the representation of women in state assemblies and Parliament remains dismal. It is said that women have an insignificant presence in decision-making positions in political parties. It recommended reserving at least 50% of seats for women in local bodies, state legislative assemblies, Parliament, parliamentary levels, and all government decision-making bodies. The National Policy for the Empowerment of Women (2001) stated that reservation will be considered in higher legislative bodies. However, women reservation policies promoted the participation of women in the Indian political sphere, although gender discrimination was nakedly visible in every sphere of Indian legislative systems. So many factors merely reiterate women's fundamental problems: 1) No interaction with the Panchayat and other relevant officers. 2) Inactive or proxy members 3) internationalization of socially defined gender roles and an inherent acceptance of patriarchy, caste, and class barriers. 4) Non-articulation and inability to identify obstacles.

Patriarchal values have combined with political intimidation from opposing parties and vested groups, and the system itself has hampered the functioning of Elected Women Representatives.

Film and sociology are interlinked. Between realist films, four interrelated themes, i.e., identity, interaction, inequality, and institutions, help sociologists analyze society in detail. Sociologists can use films as social texts to explore these core themes. So, in this paper, I would like to explain that in the context of post-nineties Indian cinema, did they focus the debates on Women Reservation in terms of Indian politics? And the political subjugation of women through cinematic gaze? Here I would like to approach the post nineties films from a particular sense of representation. Here the term 'representation' will be used from two discourses i) Representation as 'Speaking of' as in politics and 'Representation' as in art or philosophy. Films will be discussed from the socio-historical and gender perspectives.

Key words: Women Reservation, Indian Legislation, Inequality, Indian Cinema

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Patriarchy indicates the norms for women to restrict their mobility in the social sphere; thus, their identities would be confined between four walls of rooms. Historically, women have been neglected because of their individualities, which are determined by male members such as father-husband-son. Such exclusions are based on essentialist assumptions about women. They are not deemed capable of exercising rights to self-determination or engaging the public democratic or political process of their inferiority to men. Nevertheless, in the mid-1970s, the agenda of political empowerment of women focused on the term of gender justice. Conceptually, the term empowerment is a process that enables women to consider their access and control to material, intellectual and human resources. Empowerment is the redistribution of power that challenges patriarchal ideology and male dominance. Patriarchy is indicated as ramparts between public and private for women. The inner-outer distinction specified that the world is external, the domain of material, and the home represents the inner spiritual self. The world is typically a treacherous terrain of pursuing material interests where practical consideration reigns supreme. It is also eventually the domain of the male. The home, in its essence, remains unaffected by the profane activities of the material world, and woman is its representation (though indirectly, it is controlled by men).

In the film '*Samsodhan*' (1996), director Govind Nihalani tried to establish the argument that after the implementation of women's reservation in the Panchayat election, the inferior position of women could not change because, in many male members of political parties, they had chosen women candidates from their own families or communities thus they controlled the power. After the implementation of seat reservations for women in Panchayat at the National level, the first argument against quota from several feminist groups is known as the 'proxy argument'. Scholars like Madhu Kiswar and Nivedita Menon argued that many female candidates would be contested by proxy for their husbands, fathers, or fathers-in-law. The critics focused on the question of which women would benefit from women's quotas since the bill did not specify criterion eligibility other than sex. Thus, Madhu Kiswar, editor of '*Manushi*' argued that familialism was likely to eradicate the democratizing potential of the bill.

She claimed, "...chances are that we will be saddled with more biwi-beti brigades because leaders will likely resort to fielding their mothers, sisters, or wives to ensure that the women's quota stays within control." (Kiswar: 1996)ⁱ Scholars like Jay Prakash Narayan, Dhirubhai Seth, and Yogendra Yadav also argued that in such a situation, there was likely to be greater resentment against women, undermining the very objective of the Bill. Those men who got pushed out of their constituencies or observed their allies sidelined would either sabotage female contenders in revenge or spend much of their political capital to help their female relatives concerning those reserved seats. Such proxies would be expected to keep the seat safe for the men until the next election when they would again try to reclaim their seats.ⁱⁱ (Narayan Jayprakash, Seth Dhirubhai, Yadav Yogendra, Kiswar Madhu: 2004).

In the film 'Satta' (2002) and the Mrathi film 'Deol' (2004), they visualized that women were nominated as candidates in elections; thus, all power would be confined by male politicians. In the film 'Satta' (2002), the protagonist Anuradha's in-laws' family was against women's emancipation there, and her husband, MLA Vivek Chauhan, was arrested in a murder case then. Anuradha's in-laws requested her to contest in the election to save the seats, but they claimed that when Vivek would be free from jail, she had to return the seat to Vivek. Protagonist Anuradha raised questions against that proposal, which cleared that sometimes men could accept women's engagement in the public sphere or would propose to contest in the election, but the question of women's empowerment would be suppressed because the identities of women could not exist independent of ideology; therefore, men could not accept women as neutral categories that would live independently of all political consideration.

Sushma Swaraj, former MP of Bharatiya Janta party, claimed in 1996, 12th September, that women's representation was long overdue and resulted from male control within political parties. She assumed that in the case of Panchayat legislation, women's bills would improve over time through the implementation process and the education of future legislatures. Interestingly, the second argument came from backward-class leaders who saw the Women's Reservation Bill as a kind of elite conspiracy. They thought that reservation would likely primarily benefit women who belonged to the privileged or honoured section of society. Gender justice would thus be a mere face, they said, and social justice might suffer from women's quotas. Thus, OBC leaders had been demanding from 1996 onwards that a sub-quota be defined within the women's quota for backward caste women along with existing sub-quotas for SC and ST women (most recently sub, sub-quota was also demanded for women belonging to minority communities). Uma Bharti first claimed that the legislation did not provide guarantees for Backward Class women. Her argument was the most oppressed segment of society was backward-class women, and their voices were the most limited in Government. A leader of Rashtriya Janta Dal Raghuvansh Pratap Singh declared: "...only parties led by Brahmins would oppose separate reservations for OBCs, Dalits and minorities...After all, the concept of reservation is a means for those who cannot make it on their own...It is not for those who can contest and win from a general seat. Why should anybody object to giving the deprived their share in power?"ⁱⁱⁱ

Director Govind Nihalani raised the pertinent points in terms of his film 'Samsodhan' (1996) that in the case of caste, for instance, the heavy emphasis on the historical past and backwardness of caste discrimination, which was to be rectified by compensatory policies, might help us understand the peculiar place of caste in the imagination of the nation-state in the decades following independence.^{iv} The preferential programmes and politics aimed at the scheduled caste and scheduled tribes were never premised on the recognition of injustice in the modern present. Backward Class Commission regionalized, unable to carry out assigned tasks meaningfully, hampered by the negative attitudes of the State, the indifference, if not hostility, of academia and the national press.

Most difficult of all, upper caste domination became largely invisible in the casteless ethos. There was little support for constitutionally sanctioned reservations, even from left and democratic organizations, and attitudes had changed only after the Mandal Agitation.^v

As a result of legislative terms, Parliament could not simply pass a Women's Bill containing a provision for a quota for Backward Classes within it without also amending the equal rights and non-discrimination provisions of the constitution. This latter requirement would have such wide-ranging implications that politicians did not raise it explicitly. The initial protest of Margaret Alva to Uma Bharti commented that if members of OBCs wanted to ensure their representation, a measure to provide special provisions for OBCs should be raised separately in Parliament.^{vi} The demand for a quota within quota hobbled the Women's Bill and prevented its passage. For that reason, several supporters of the Women's Bill considered the whole issue a political tactic to stop the legislation. Brinda Karat wrote in August 2000 that "the crucial issue here is that once a seat is reserved for women, all contesting parties will be forced to file them." (Karat:2000)^{vii} Here, she referred to the parties that had already drawn their strengths from the OBC communities and highlighted the success of women in SC seats. Karat said that throughout India's independent history, women had been disproportionately represented in SC/ST seats. Karat suggested the same would be true for Backward Class candidates in women's seats.

In the context of Indian films, visualised the participation of women in politics as confined to elite-class women, and the political rights of backwards, Dalit or minority women were suppressed and neglected by hierarchies. Films like 'Deoal' (2004), 'and Raajniti (2011) highlighted the monopoly of elite-class women in Indian politics and similarly visualized problems of post-colonial marginalization of minorities and the consolidation of Hindu dominance. Significantly, nineties Indian parallel films visualized hierarchical and male dominance in Indian politics simultaneously a short film 'Pankh: Ek Urda.' (2007)^{viii} there highlighted that OBC men did not want reservations for women. OBC women were insulted by repeated statements of those claiming to respect them, who virtually said that, in comparison to women of the upper castes, they were not capable of winning seats. The short film was shot at Khagar village in Bihar. There, when Zinna, an OBC woman, wanted to contest the Panchayat election, she was threatened by other OBC male members of the village. Nevertheless, when she complained about her harassment, she was kidnapped and brutally sexually assaulted by other backward-class male members. But the primary positive side of the film is that with the influence of her determination, Zinnat was able to contest the Panchayat election in the end. As the first female OBC candidate, she was elected Panch in Khagaria village. The film highlighted that the problem was not that backwards-class women could not win seats but that OBC men who distributed tickets refused to share the benefits of the increased clout they had achieved in the post-Mandal mobilizations. *Even in the case of nominations to legislative Councils or Rajyasabha, what did one make of the fact that only last month, the last woman to be nominated from Bihar for the Rajya Sabha by the RJD belongs to the upper cast? The film's director raised a pertinent question: What prevented those who had declared war ostensibly on behalf of OBC women from nominating one in the parliament?*

Recent web series 'Panchayat' (2021) depicted the important question against reservation was the 'efficiency' argument, which underlining the difficulty of finding enough suitable candidates and, therefore, the risk of incompetent people being elected. Madhu Kiswar argued that "we should try to bring a qualitative change with women's participation in elected assemblies rather than bring it down further with simply joining as puppets in that unholy enterprise." (Kiswar Madhu: 1996)^{ix} the director of the Webseries Panchayat, Deepak kumar Mishra depicted the debate about 'efficiency and merit' tied into the understanding of discrimination.^x

Short film 'Mujhe Pankh De dyo: Chavi Rajawat episode'^{xi} there visualised that when Chavi wished to contest in the Panchayat election, she faced the question of her efficiency, though Chavi was post-graduated in business administration. Govind Nihalani's film 'Samsodhan' (1996) also visualized that when protagonist Vidya won the Panchayat election and started to interfere in village development, then other male Panch members and Sarpanch raised questions about Vidya's efficiency. They claimed since women were suitable at home as wives-mothers-daughter-in-laws and they were not comfortable in the public sphere or external affairs as 'bumiputra', it was their duty to make every decision on behalf of women panch in the issue of development in their village.^{xii}

Mulayam Singh Yadav, leader of the Samajwadi Party, his opinion was against women's reservation because he thought that politics would make women crazy. Instead, women were essential in transforming society and looking after the next generation. Rather than pursuing a political role, he consoled women to work harder at home. It was significant that male politicians claimed that women were suitable at home or accidentally if they would come into politics. Hence, they had to handle accessible departments like culture, social welfare, etc.; they argued from their fear that if they gave an inch, women would take a mile. Politicians at the Panchayat level who thought women could pose no danger at the lowest tier of Government had already realised that. Even before some status, women began to exceed one-third of seats by contesting and winning from general seats. If that repeats parliament and assemblies frequently, the gender balance will change.^{xiii} Apart from 'YadavTroyika', many other men and women objected in particular to the mechanism of rotation of sets to be reserved for women. They argued that that would undermine democracy, as it would not allow MPs to nurture their constituencies.

Both the filmmakers, Nihalani and Umesh Kulkarni mentioned the pertinent issue in their films that after the recommendation of the 81st Amendment Bill to the Indian Constitution in favour of one-third representation for women in Indian Parliamentary systems, many arguments came against it. Nevertheless, women activists and politicians finally recognised that the electoral quotas for women were a form of affirmative action aimed at increasing women's representation in elected legislative bodies. Feminists argued that if the elected represented the ideas of the people they represented, then there was no reason why males should not express women's ideas as women were no more underrepresented than any other group whose ideas did not get a fair hearing. Even if women had distinct interests and or needs, it could be argued that men should, in principle, be able to voice them. Philips reminded us that 'with a strong dose of political realism', women could not expect 'the degree of vigorous advocacy that people bring to their concern.'

For this reason, the presence of women in elected politics was vital. She also argued that changing the gender composition of legislative bodies was a significant and necessary challenge to the social arguments which had systematically placed women in a subordinate position. Whilst the presence of women was also significant as a symbolic representation and related to the self-image of the represented, it should not be seen as an end. So, the representation was the process needing constant reinvigoration by the elector's participation in holding the elected accountable.^{xiv} Philips comprehended that it was exciting when more female candidates were elected. Their example raised women's self-esteem, encouraged others to follow in their footsteps, and dislodged deep-rooted assumptions about what was appropriate for women and men. It also presented gender parity as a straightforward matter of justice: that it was patently and grotesquely unfair for men to monopolize representation.^{xv}

Norwegian sociologist Hernes clarified that all dealing with the objectives of a massive presence of women in political assemblies into three main categories. The first argument focused on 'gender justice': women present in elected assemblies had to be in proportion to their place in society if 'people's representation' central to the democratic principle was to be meaningful. In 1997, the Deputy Speaker of Rajya Sabha Nazma Heptullah declared that "Reservation for women would right the wrong and change the imbalance in legislative representation overnight...we must have more women if we want democracy to flourish." (Heptullha Nazma: 1997)^{xvi}. The second argument focused on women's interests: in that line of reasoning, women were considered an interest group, and a significant presence of women in political assemblies was deemed necessary for their interests to be adequately represented. Neera Chandhoke wrote, "It is not as if women have not occupied seats in legislatures; it is simply that they have not addressed that question which pertains to women's problems adequately, seriously or sensitively. Had they done so, we would not have had all these missing women or illiteracy or hunger or homelessness or violence both at home and at the workplace. The demand behind the Women's Reservation Bill is that women representatives should address the specific problems of the constituency". (Chandhoke Neera: 2000)^{xvii} The third argument focused on women as a resource of political life: women possess specific qualities or talents that could be fruitfully tapped by society through their more effective political participation. According to T.N. Seshan, former Chief Election Commissioner, "Everybody knows that women are less easily carried away and are more objective than men. They will make politics more sober." (Season: 1996)^{xviii}. Season's argument was correct, proved in the aspect of Indian politics. In the post-independence arena, women politicians like Sonia Gandhi, Brinda Karat, Chhavi Rajawat, Subhashini Ali, Malini Bhattacharya, Krishna Tirat, Meera Kumar, GirijaVyash, Mohini Giri, Mamta Jayswal, Mamta Banerjee, Mayavati from top-level women political activists to grass root levels politicians like Bilashibala Sahish, Deblina Hembram, Rinku Naskar, Rampari, Geeta Devi etc they already proved that political participation means to achieve involvement of decision-making activities of the Government. And they could earn the same respect as men in the political field. It was proved that 'Reservation for women' was better grasped if we re-conceptualised what it means to act politically in the interests of women. Fraser's heterogeneous ideology helped accommodate women's various political actions to fight the constraints on their political life. According to the argument of Michelle Bachelet, General and Under Secretary General of UN Women, it could mention that quotas have spurred one of the greatest successes globally in women's empowerment and grassroots democracy in India. She said about the proposed 'women's Reservation Bill, "If it becomes law, it could potentially lead to one of the most significant changes in India since independence in 1947. It will send a strong message to women in India and to the world that India is leading the way for democracy for women and equality."^{xix} (Bachelet Michelle: 2012)

Feminist groups had been arguing that quotas for women were needed to compensate for the social barriers that prevented women from participating in politics and thus made their voices heard. In the film 'Satta' (2004), they visualise that when protagonist Anuradha is confused about participating in politics, her friend Paul tells her that Anu will get her self-existence with involvement in politics. *The film has shown that* after taking initiatives for Reservation, it would be clear that quotas had been to increase the number of women in parliament gradually. Then, the gender variable was the most important one to consider when voting.^{xx} Simultaneously, as the consensus around the need for quota had evolved, it also raised new and important issues for women's groups and movements.

ADWA's former general secretary, Sudha Sundararaman, claimed that "...all women across states and the entire country support the bill. May Dalit and Muslim women also want the bill to be implemented as everyone stands to gain from it." (Sundararaman Sudha: 2010)^{xxi}. Director Prakash Jha depicted in his film *Rajneeti* (2010), that in India, reservation for women through political parties might not be advisable as most of our political parties lack inner-party democracy. Therefore, quotas implemented through them might give the party high command a virtual monopoly in nominating all the candidates for reserved seats. He mentioned that instituting reservations assumed women as candidates would come forth to vie for the reserved seats-which women had a desire to participate, and that reservation assured them the opportunity. In the twenty-first Century, in the Indian political context, the phrase empowerment has been used to describe the main objective of reservation for women in Parliament. However, the agitation for increased representation of women in legislatures should also face the reality of how Parliament works. That Parliament has not been able to meet even for 100 days a year because of disruptions is a severe dampener of such expectations. The right to represent a constituency of voters in Parliament is undoubtedly a great privilege, but unless women are also helped to liberate themselves from the various disadvantages. Improving women's opportunities in the area of decision-making requires long-term strategies. They have to be systematic, and they must aim at challenging prevailing structures. Concrete measures are needed to remove many obstacles that make the process of participation difficult.

New strategies and mechanisms need to be developed to increase women's access to decision-making positions within different political power structures. Some of these mechanisms may be set up by the Government, such as quotas, while others should arise from the collective action of women.^{xxii} Besides demanding quotas/ one-third reservation for women in the legislative bodies, women must demand sufficient quotas in ministerial positions or actual seats of power. Women need to get into decision-making positions by any means possible. With adequate decision-making power and control at all levels, women's gains are easily ignored and eroded. All significant economic and political decisions in India (for that matter, in the whole world) are being made without the input of women. Women should wield political power in decision-making positions, too. A strong group of women in politics can make a difference by bringing women's perspective to all issues on the political agenda: foreign affairs, economics, trade, justice, military, peace, etc. Women should advocate for a polity based on gender parity in decision-making bodies and processes.

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ⁱⁱⁱ Frontline 6th May, 2003

^{iv} The point that Ambedkar recognised was that the caste system is perpetuated by endogamy; at one point he advocated inter caste marriage as the only programme of action that could lead to the elimination of caste. Later on, it seems that he saw the inadequacy of this line of action taken on its own: yet even today it is an act that is perceived by the forces upholding the caste system as a threat to the prevailing order and invites the severest punishment. The imposition of the rule of caste endogamy entail the control of women's sexual behaviour and in fact all aspects of their social behaviour by the patriarchal caste Panchayat. The Hindu Code Bill entailed a clear declaration that the law of the Panchayat would be limited in independent India, that this Code for the Hindu majority would hold precedence over patriarchal caste Panchayats or undeclared caste authorities. It is no wonder that it invited such bitter opposition from the defenders of the traditional Hindu social order. Caste is perpetuated through endogamy, but then it operates through several social and economic institutions and ensures, first and foremost, that the domination of the upper castes and the subservience of the lowest castes is preserved. Women of the lower castes remain at the bottom of the hierarchical order; they have no right to privacy or decision-making and no right of protection against sexual exploitation. This can be seen in the question put by a judge to Bhanwari Devi when she went to court against her upper caste rapists: "How far apart were your legs when the rape took place?" The practice of caste builds up what Pierre Bourdieu calls a 'doxa', a set of shared beliefs and norms within a community which condition the behaviour of its members without being openly declared.

A member violating the rules of the doxa invites social sanctions of various kinds, including the most violent. But the doxa operates on an unarticulated level apart from one's consciously declared beliefs. This level is different from the Freudian concept of the unconscious which refers to the formation of the individual personality in the European context. Perhaps the concept of 'neniv' as opposed to 'janiv' as used by Sharad Patil (and borrowed by him from Buddhist philosophy) comes closer to what we need to analyse this situation. For the doxa or the neniv is social in content: in Indian society it incorporates all the aspects of caste identity, caste prejudice, hierarchy, and submission to a patriarchal order which are so much a part of the lived life of constitutionally equal Indian citizens.

Fifty years after independence and after the defeat of the Hindu Code Bill, these realities of Indian society are pushing themselves into the political arena. The result is a disruption of the consensus on the secular and democratic basis of Indian political life, which existed for some decades after 1947; the disruption makes room for the coming to power of the BJP by default, so to speak. Nivedita Menon (1997), for example, voicing what she calls her ambivalence on the question of reservations for women in parliament, says "We may need to think in terms of quotas within quotas - OBC within women's quotas, woman's quotas within all others and so on - and most certainly of how to ensure the possibility that newer groups can always present themselves to be recognised." The need for a pluralist approach is important when we are seeking to extend the scope of our democracy, as Nivedita Menon implies in the quoted passage. Those who see themselves as a group seeking political representation should have the chance to do so, the openings for this should be built into our political institutions. But do 'women' really constitute such a group in reality? Don't caste groups have more claim to being marginalised categories with a social cohesiveness and common modes of being oppressed, which entitles them to seek political recognition as a group? The issue is not just one of identity politics, a term now used without much clarity to describe the contemporary phenomenon of the political assertion of various marginalised social groups which identify themselves on the basis of caste or community (dalits, Muslims, Adivasis, OBCs). Ambedkar's concern here is with the social inequalities that perpetuate themselves in spite of legislation to the contrary, in spite of the declared 'secular' politics of the major political parties - even those on the left.

^v V P Singh Government when it sought to put the recommendations of the Mandal Commission into practice. One would have thought that the Mandal Commission had committed the sin of creating caste divisions where none existed. While reservations in Government and semi-Government jobs have a definite role for members of the backward castes in creating a bit of space for upward mobility, the violent passions that appeared to agitate the anti-reservationists were surely wildly out of proportion to the actual threat to the job opportunities of upper-caste students, especially at a time when the total number of jobs in the public sector was stagnant and expected to dwindle in the future. Here too, what was being threatened was an unstated right, a part of the doxa: the right of the upper castes to dominate in the administration and in education. On the other hand, the BJP faces no such problem when it takes up the issue of women's reservations. The opposition to the bill is now taking shape around a different set of issues, with the demand for reservations for OBC women within the reservations for women in parliament.

^{vi} Protests over provisions for OBCs showed dramatic consequences in both 1989 and 2006. The 93rd Amendment to the constitution passed on 20th January 2006 might open the door to the range of reservations for Backward Class.

^{vii} Karat Brinda, 1st August, Hindu

^{viii} Dibyajyoti Basu, 2007, Pankh: EkUdan...

^{ix} Kiswar Madhu Purnima, October 1996, Women and Politics beyond Quota', EPW, Vol-31, no-43-26, p-2872.

^x Discrimination is understood as different treatment of equals, and affirmative action is represented as a form of discrimination, albeit positive discrimination. As a consequent in countries grounded in equal opportunity premises, affirmative action proposals tend to be located as exemption within anti discrimination status.

^{xi} Kapoor Ekta, 2012 *Mujhe Pank De dyo: ChaaviRajwat*

^{xii} Engels believed that women's subordination began with the development of private property. He said both the division of classes and subordination of women developed historically. When men started domesticating animals, they also understood the principle of impregnation. They developed weapons for big hunt, which were then also used in inter-groups fights. Slavery developed. Gens started acquiring animals and slaves, especially female slaves. That led to more division among the sexes. Men acquired power over others and started accumulating wealth in the forms of animals and slaves. All those led to the formation of private property. Men wanted to retain power and property and passed it on to their own children. To ensure that inheritance the mother's right was overthrown. In order to establish the right of father, women had to be domesticated and confined and their movements, affairs and sexualities were regulated and controlled. Surplus was controlled by men. Women became economically dependent. Modern civilization according to Engels was based on restricting women to the sphere of home in order to produce heirs to inherit property. Engels mentioned it was the beginning of the sexual double standard in marriage. According to him, with the development of the state, the monogamous family changed into the patriarchal family in which the wife's household labour became a private service the wife became a servant, excluded from all participation in the social production.

^{xiii} **The issue was not one of gender balance. The 108th Constitution Amendment, or the Women's Reservation Bill, was an essential part of legislation not just because it was a tool to help more women get elected but also because it was a tool to change how the system had functioned so far.**

^{xiv} Philips Anne, 2008, Quotas for Women, in the book of Reservations For women, Edited by Meena Dhanda, Kali for Women, New Delhi, p-82

^{xv} Ibid, Philips argued that in politics if there was no obstacles operating to keep certain groups of people out of political lives and women would expect positions of political influence to be randomly distributed between the sexes. There might be some minor and deviation but any more distorted distribution was evidence of intentional or structural discrimination. In such context women were being denied rights and opportunities that were available to men.

^{xvi} Economic Times 1997, 16th March

^{xvii} Chandhoke Neera, 2000 6th December, The Hindu

^{xviii} Season T.N. 1996, 15th October, India Today.

^{xix} Bachelet Michelle, 2012, 4th October, World waiting for India to pass Women's Reservation Bill, Indian Express.

^{xx} However, the women's groups in India have had close link with political parties. So the question of representativeness was also tied closely with the question of political platforms. "In a system which is party based, where her it is men or women, they will represent the view point of the party...Women voters while making their choice of candidates will have to judge which of those platforms is intrinsically against women's equality and vote against the candidates regardless of whether it is a man or woman."

Karat Brinda, 2005, 'Vote for politics not Gender', in the book of Survival and Emancipation Note's from Indian Women's Struggles, Three Eassays, New Delhi, p-150

^{xxi} Sundararaman Sudha, 2010, Campaign for women's Reservation Bill launched. The Hindu

^{xxii} Some such strategies can be stated as follows :

- Women representatives should form into a 'critical mass' so as to act as a pressure group in the legislature. A critical mass of women in politics can bring to the agenda issues of crucial concern to women which are often otherwise neglected or relegated to second place, such as contraception, abortion, violence against women, gender discrimination, maternity leave, child care etc., for, women legislators are more responsive than men to the needs of all persons in society.
- Devise, launch and promote public campaigns to alert public opinion to the usefulness and advantages for society as a whole of balanced participation by women and men in decision- making.
- Women should form their own political parties such as those existing in Canada, Germany, Iceland, Nigeria, the Philippines, Russia and Spain. Women's support groups should be formed throughout the country to work as lobbying groups in conjunction with political parties. Their aims should be to increase the political participation of women at various levels of the power structure and to support women eager to take part in politics.
- Women should organise and establish networks at different levels to influence the decision-making process. There is a great need to increase solidarity among women's groups for the cause of women.
- Forming a women's shadow cabinet as was the case with the Czech women. The Czech Social Democratic Party has long had an internal quota of 35 percent women in all party bodies and also has a women's bureau. But when a few years ago, it became the Government, not one woman was appointed to the cabinet. The women promptly formed a shadow cabinet, to show that there were just as many women as men qualified to head departments.
- Expansion of educational opportunities for women, greater recognition of their unpaid work, wider representation in electoral politics, legislative and legal mechanisms to safeguard their rights and equal opportunities for participation in the decision-making process are some other things which would strengthen the process of empowerment.